

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis of some New Arylazoisoxazoles

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BIOLOGICAL importance of azo compounds is well-known¹ and other useful chemotherapeutics², e.g. *N,N*-bis(2-chlorophenyl)-*p*-phenylazoaniline has been found to possess tumor inhibitory activity³. Furthermore, isoxazoles also have pharmacological⁴ interest and are found in nature⁵. It has been observed that the activity of azo linkage increases on the incorporation of suitable heterocyclic nuclei⁶. These studies prompted us to synthesise some new

compounds (1) as possible antineoplastic agents in which the isoxazole moiety is linked at one side of azo linkage in order to enhance the overall activity of the azo group.

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where R and R' represent various substituents.

The compounds reported herein have been synthesised by reacting various substituted anilines with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The structure of these compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analysis, and ir, nmr and mass spectral studies.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Parkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, uv-vis spectra on a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer, nmr spectra (using TMS as internal standard) on a Perkin-Elmer R-35 instrument and mass spectra (70 eV) on a Jeol IMS-D × 300 spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

1-Aminophenyl-3-arylhydrazonobutane-1,3-dione: Appropriate derivative of aniline (0.01 ml) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml), and water (5 ml), and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, cooled aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) was added. The resulting diazonium salt was filtered in already cooled solution mixture of sodium acetate (6.94 g) and alcohol (25 ml) containing 2,4-pentanedione (0.01 mol). The product

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-ARYLAZOISOXAZOLES (1)*

Sl. no.	R	R ₁	M.p. °C	Yield %	Colour	Mol. formula
1.	H	H	88	70	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O
2.	2-OH	H	140	60	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂
3.	3-Cl	H	185	64	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
4.	4-Cl	H	190	62	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
5.	2-OH ₂	H	164	66	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O
6.	4-OH ₂	H	160	68	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O
7.	4-OH ₂ -3-NO ₂	H	161	63	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂
8.	4-Cl-2-NO ₂	H	191	60	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
9.	3-NO ₂	H	238	67	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
10.	4-NO ₂	H	200	67	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂
11.	2-OCH ₃	H	107	62	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂
12.	4-Br	H	244	68	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OClBr
13.	H	2-Cl	181	71	Brown	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl
14.	2-NO ₂	2-Cl	210	66	Orange	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
15.	3-NO ₂	2-Cl	201	64	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
16.	2-CH ₃	2-Cl	164	62	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl
17.	4-CH ₃	2-Cl	135	63	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OCl
18.	2-OCH ₃	2-Cl	168	60	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
19.	4-CH ₃ -3-NO ₂	2-Cl	210	61	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl
20.	4-Br	2-Cl	285	66	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OBrCl
21.	3-Cl	2-Cl	187	63	Yellow	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OCl ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and C analyses.

precipitated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals, $C_{16}H_{15}N_3O_2$, m.p. 110° (Calcd: C, 64.64; H, 5.05; N, 14.14; O, 16.16%).

4-Arylazo-5-methyl-3-aminophenylisoxazole: Appropriate derivative of 1-aminophenyl-3-arylhydrazono-butane-1,3-dione* (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 ml) in alcohol (25 ml) and sodium acetate (2.0 g) for 4 h. The product after cooling was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from dimethylformamide, m.p. 88° (Found: N, 20.01; C, 69.00; H, 4.70. $C_{16}H_{14}N_4O$ calcd. for: N, 20.14; C, 69.06; H, 5.00%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 400 nm (N=N); M^+ at *m/e* 278; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 595 (N=N), 1 610 (C=C or C=N); 3 415 (NH) and 750–800 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); a sharp singlet at δ 2.5 (3H, 3CH₃), one signal at δ 3.0 (1H, NH) and a group of signals at δ 7.5–8.0 (10H, 2C₆H₅) were also observed.

Similarly other substituted azo compounds having substituents 2-OH, 2-OCH₃, 2-Cl, 4-Cl, 2-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 4-CH₃-3-NO₂, 4-Cl-2-NO₂, 3-NO₂, 4-NO₂, and 4-Br were prepared by taking suitable hydrazone. One more series of compounds, viz. 4-arylazo-5-methyl-3-amino(2-chlorophenyl)isoxazoles were prepared by the similar method. Characteristics of the synthesised compounds are given in Table 1.

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Synthesis of [S-(2-Acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)]-N-aryldithiocarbamates

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MANY 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been reported to possess various biological activities¹⁻³. Dithiocarbamates themselves and their incorporation with various heterocyclic moieties lead to some important biologically active agents⁴. Keeping this in view, we have studied synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some [S-(2-acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)]-N-aryldithiocarbamates. The compounds were synthesised as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Reagents: (i) ONBr, KHCO₃, (ii) ClCH₂COCl, C₆H₆, (iii) NH₂-S-CS-NHR.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the synthesised compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds showing characteristic band at 1 280 (N=N=C), 1 520 (C=N cyclic), 1 320 (pentacyclic ring), 1 740 (C=O), 3 260–3 340 (NH; str), 1 650 (CO=N), 1 160 (C=S) and 740 cm^{-1} (ortho-disubstituted benzene), supported the validity of the compounds.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (1): It was prepared by following the reported method⁵.

2-Chloroacetamido-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2): It was chloroacetylated by the reported procedure⁶.